

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL-CULTURAL TOURISM

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Abstract

This article reveals the concept of historical and cultural tourism, its role in the field of Tourism. Factors affecting the development of historical-cultural tourism have been studied on the basis of PEST analysis. Opportunities and prospects for the development of historical and cultural tourism are analyzed.

Keywords: tourism, cultural heritage, tourist product, historical-cultural tourism, historical monument, statistics, restoration.

Introduction

The tourism industry is one of the leading sectors of world economy and is a promising sector that brings high income to the national economy. Tourism accounts for about 5% of the world's GDP, with nearly 10% of the population in developed countries employed in tourism. According to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to further improve the public administration system in the fields of Tourism, Sports and cultural heritage" dated April 6, PF-6199, the cultural heritage agency was established under the Ministry of Tourism and sports. It is important to carry out systematic scientific and methodological research on the further development of historical and cultural tourism in our country, such as the identification, accounting, protection, promotion of objects of material cultural heritage as the main tasks of the agency, such as the state register, electronic catalog, maintaining the state cadastre, marking protected tegras, as well as state control in the field. Thus, it is relevant to analyze the current state of historical and cultural tourism, the prospects for its development and its impact on the national economy. First of all, it is necessary to determine the content of the concept of "prehistoric tourism". A review of the literature on the topic should be noted that in the current pandemic, there is no single concept among many authors regarding the preservation of the sectors that make up the tourism infrastructure from the crisis. In our opinion, the scope of research that still needs to be carried out in this regard is wide, and we must also take into account international experiences in ensuring the development of Tourism networks. In the economic literature, issues related to historical-cultural tourism have been studied by a number of scholars and given different definitions. Dutch researcher Richard Greg describes historical-cultural tourism as "the way people go to cultural, attractions far from their usual place of residence with the aim of gathering new information and experience to meet their cultural needs" [8]. Russian specialist Y.V. Kolotova defines historical-cultural tourism as "the potential of the socio-cultural environment, connected by traditions and Customs, the peculiarities of the household, which include all the possibilities of the country." I.T. Frolova, on the other hand, believes that historical cultural tourism consists of directions such as: 1) enrichment of knowledge about culture and cultural heritage, 2) protection and restoration of culture, 3)

dialogue of cultures, depending on the global scale as a factor and means of bringing peoples closer together. In other words, at present, the main humanitarian functions of cultural tourism, as the following are noted: - cultural-educational and educational; - cultural protection and preservation; - establishment of ties and peacekeeping. G.Karpov. L.The khorovas, on the other hand, consider historical and cultural tourism as “cultural attractions, museums and historical sites, art galleries, music and drama theaters, concert venues, performing arts, classical values and traditional recreation areas of local residents reflecting historical heritage, visits to houses of innovative artistic creativity” for people to gain new information, experience and impressions. Scientists and researchers of our country I.To xliyev, R.Amrididnova, Sh.Ro ziyev, A.Khamidov, N. Ibadullayev F.Aziztoeva, B. In the scientific works of Mamatov and others, many issues related to the theoretical and practical aspects of the development of the tourism industry are covered, but, since some issues related to the development of historical and cultural tourism have not been sufficiently studied, some problems still remain relevant today. The interest of tourists in different cities, remote parts of the world and the peoples who live in them is the strongest incentive for travel. Therefore, tourism is the best way to get acquainted with other cultures, with the history and life of other peoples, with works of art. Acquaintance with the history, culture and customs of another country enriches the spiritual world of a person. One of the important advantages of historical cultural tourism over other types of recreation is that it is in demand all year round, and its significant difference is that it is not seasonal. This tour is relevant at any time of the year, since tourists can take an excursion to visit museums, see historical monuments and sights of the country. The role of historical as well as archaeological objects present in the regions is important in the development of historical-cultural tourism. Their historicity, place in the history of the area and the level of preservation will help increase the number of tourists interested in it the presence of several objects in one destination for any visiting tourist will prolong the duration of its travel time. And this process is tourist 1 source: author's development as a result of research Tourism Art and literature •famous literary works, theater, film figures; sculptures; examples of Arts and crafts, theaters, studios, etc. historical tourism •monuments of human civilization and socio-economic culture; ancient cities, ruins of ancient cities; monuments of military culture (castles, fortified walls and castles, battles, etc.) Tourism of architectural culture •architectural ensembles, palace complexes, shrines and temples; small architectural forms (buildings, towers, arches, halls, pantheons, mausoleums, Memorial caves); hydraulic structures (dams, canals, hydroelectric power plants); port industrial architecture; recreational architecture tourist theme parks culture •artificial landscapes (residential areas, sports and recreation areas, industrial areas, transport structures) urban and cultural tourism •urban environment and urban culture; urban panoramas; Organization of Landscape Planning. Museum tourism •the holding of museums, exhibitions, historical and cultural events and presentations gives the opportunity to export services more a In developed countries, 3-5% of jobs belong to the tourism industry; - tourism indirectly affects the development of other sectors in the process of its development (construction, transport, Road, Food Trade Industry, etc.);-the tourism industry has a high growth rate, the pandemic crisis in countries of the world in the previous period, foreign exchange revenues from tourism increased by an average of 8-12; - ensures structural changes in the national economy” - attracting foreign investment and generating income in foreign currency; - improves the economic and social image of the country in foreign

countries; - promotes the emergence and development of national parks and reserves;-serves the preservation of works of art and customs, etc. It is also necessary to cite some negative factors that affect the development of historical and cultural tourism. In particular, the preservation, reconstruction of historical and cultural objects requires significant investments. Some developing countries may not be able to allocate sufficient funds to sustain them due to capital shortages. Also, the development of the industry directly depends on public policy. The rational policy of the state leads to the development of the historical and cultural tourism sector, increased international cooperation, the effective use of innovations and information technologies in the field, and, on the contrary, non-rational policies lead to the fact that tourism objects and monuments remain unattended, looted. It seems that various factors influence the development of historical-cultural tourism. The implementation of PEST analysis of historical and cultural tourism in our country makes it possible to form a complete picture of the state of development of this area. Conclusions and suggestions when researching the possibilities of effective use of historical and cultural tourism sites, it is necessary to identify ways to increase their effective use, factors affecting them and their identification, as well as to group resources to assess the possibilities of using tourist resources and determine indicative indicators of their conservation, restoration activities. As a result of the theoretical and practical study of improving the economic efficiency of the industry, the following conclusions were drawn and recommendations were developed: - improving the quality and exemplary service of museums and cultural heritage objects and strengthening their reputation through this; - organizing cultural events such as an International Exhibition, Conference, festival in the demonstration of the country's historical heritage in the world; - by significantly increasing the role of archaeological monuments in the field of historical cultural tourism, bringing them to the level of the brand among foreign and domestic tourists; - preparing archaeological monuments for a museum exhibition in part (conservation and restoration); - introducing national craft traditions to the world with the establishment of master classes in folk art centers for tourists; - increasing the visit of foreign tourists Quality Organization of excursion services by qualified specialists; -to establish the widespread use of radio, TV and internet networks of Popular Science Information in stimulating the activities of tourist information centers on historical cultural tourism. In a general conclusion from the above, the development of historical-cultural tourism will have to be viewed not only as one of those areas that can offer the possibility of increasing socio-economic stability to support the cultural sphere.nd the impetus for the development of adjacent networks as well. Taking into account the high potential for the development of historical and cultural tourism in our country, it is possible to note the positive and negative effects of tourism on the economy on the basis of data analysis of economic literature:-an increase in the level of employment due to an increase in jobs.

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